

ELIXIR Commissioned Service [DATAREX - Data Management for Research within ELIXIR, WP2 RDM Knowledge Management and Training]

D2.4 End report on Published Learning Paths in TeSS

Executive Summary

This deliverable documents the development and publication of the ELIXIR Data Management for Researchers Learning Path in TeSS, produced in close collaboration between the ELIXIR RDM Community and the ELIXIR Training Platform, aligned with the ELIXIR Training Platform Programme 24-28. The objective was to provide a structured, sustainable, and community-driven framework to support RDM and FAIR training across ELIXIR.

The background to this work lies in the extensive RDM training materials developed across ELIXIR Nodes, particularly during the [ELIXIR-CONVERGE project](#) and several national ELIXIR node projects. While these efforts resulted in a rich training landscape, the materials were fragmented and difficult for learners to navigate as a coherent learning journey. The key problem addressed by this deliverable was therefore the lack of a visible, structured mechanism to organise and present RDM training resources across ELIXIR members.

A traditional alternative would have been the development of an institution-specific learning path authored and maintained by a single expert. However, this approach would have limited reuse, reduced visibility across ELIXIR, and risked duplication of effort. Instead, this deliverable adopted the ELIXIR Learning Paths framework, enabling a distributed, multi-institutional, and collaborative model for Learning Path development.

The major outcome of this work is the publication of the first [ELIXIR Learning Path in TeSS](#), with a second Data Stewardship Learning Path in progress. The resulting model supports community ownership, allows learning paths to evolve as resources change,

and reflects the diversity of practices and expertise across national Nodes. These characteristics align closely with ELIXIR's mission to coordinate, integrate, and sustain life science data resources and training across Europe. In addition, this deliverable provides a reusable blueprint for future ELIXIR Community Learning Paths and strengthens the long-term sustainability and impact of ELIXIR training provision.

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

(Remove section if not applicable)

LP	Learning Path
RDM	Research Data Management
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
RI	Research Infrastructure
DS	Data Stewardship
TeSS	Training eSupport System

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Introduction

The aim of this deliverable was for the ELIXIR RDM Community and its DATAREX Implementation Study to work in close collaboration with the ELIXIR Training Platform to develop a Research Data Management (RDM) Learning Path (LP) within TeSS, ensuring alignment with the ELIXIR Training Programme 24-28. While the ELIXIR-CONVERGE and national projects led by several ELIXIR Nodes provided an important opportunity to develop and consolidate a wide range of training materials in the RDM domain, there remained a clear need to organise these resources into coherent and structured learning journeys for the RDM community.

Building on these efforts, this deliverable focuses on leveraging the ELIXIR Learning Paths framework developed by the [ELIXIR Learning Paths Focus group team](#), to support sustainable, community-driven RDM training. By bringing together RDM training materials developed across multiple ELIXIR Nodes into single structured Learning Paths for researchers, this work aims to improve the coordination, visibility, and uptake of RDM and FAIR training across ELIXIR.

Developing the ELIXIR RDM Learning Path as a community project

The importance of having a Learning Path for the RDM Community

Before the start of the DATAREX project, the ELIXIR RDM Community identified the development of RDM Learning Paths as a priority activity. This strategic need led to the inclusion of learning path development as a core task within DATAREX Work Package 2 (RDM knowledge management and training).

Learning Paths guide learners through a structured sequence of courses and training materials designed to be undertaken progressively in order to acquire specific knowledge and skills. Establishing and implementing Learning Paths supports learners at different career stages, facilitates professional development, and improves the overall learning experience. For the ELIXIR RDM Community, the development of RDM Learning Paths was particularly important as it enabled the structuring and alignment of RDM and DS training materials developed across multiple ELIXIR Nodes. Many of these

materials were produced during the ELIXIR-CONVERGE project, and the Learning Path provides a mechanism to make them more discoverable and reusable.

Approach for developing Learning Paths within the RDM Community

Traditionally, learning paths are designed by a single subject-matter expert with deep experience in a specific domain and a strong understanding of the institutional or research infrastructure (RI) context in which the learning is delivered. This approach supports pedagogical coherence and alignment with local practices as learning objectives, content and assessment can be tailored to organisational needs (Biggs, 1996; Merrill, 2002).

The approach adopted for the ELIXIR Data Management for Researchers Learning Path differs from these institution-specific models and follows the methodology developed by the [ELIXIR Learning Paths group](#). This methodology enables the co-creation of learning paths that aggregate and curate training resources from multiple institutions rather than being restricted to a single organisational context. This distributed, community-driven model increases the visibility and reuse of high-quality training materials developed across ELIXIR, reduces duplication of effort, and promotes interoperability and long-term sustainability of training provision. It also supports community ownership, allows learning paths to evolve as resources change, and reflects the diversity of practices and expertise across national Nodes. These characteristics align closely with ELIXIR's mission to coordinate, integrate, and sustain life science data resources and training across Europe.

Prior to the start of the DATAREX project, initial work on defining Data Management for Researchers and Data Stewardship Learning Path topics was carried out during BioHackathon Europe 2022 ([Project 32: "Training booster: developing FAIR training materials and Learning Paths"](#)). As part of this activity, concept maps were developed to identify key topics for both the Data Management for Researchers and Data Stewardship Learning Paths.

Following the introduction of the Learning Paths feature in [TeSS](#) in July 2024, that was developed as part of the ELIXIR Training Platform 22-23 and ELIXIR Infrastructure services 2019-23 programmes (a collaboration between the TeSS team and the ELIXIR Learning Paths group), the ELIXIR RDM Community began working collectively to

develop the Data Management for Researchers Learning Path and the Data Stewardship Learning Path within TeSS. Two dedicated community workshops were organised in 2025 to support this process. At the start of each workshop, participants were introduced to the ELIXIR Learning Paths protocol and overall methodology.

In the first workshop, the jigsaw method (Aronson et al., 1978) was used to enable collaborative and parallel working. Participants joined breakout groups focused on either Data Stewardship or Data Management for Researchers, where they further developed and refined the concept learning path models created during the BioHackathon. At the end of the workshop, participants reconvened to share outputs and agree on next steps.

The second workshop focused exclusively on the Data Management for Researchers Learning Path, as the outcomes of the first workshop indicated that additional work was required for the Data Stewardship Learning Path. A similar jigsaw-based approach was used, with participants joining breakout groups dedicated to specific RDM topics. The aim was to identify relevant training materials available in TeSS for each topic, followed by a plenary session to share findings and discuss gaps.

Following the workshops, the community decided to continue development through weekly one-hour meetings. Nine additional group meetings were required to produce a first draft of the Data Management for Researchers Learning Path. During these Community meetings, the training materials were reviewed to ensure alignment with the topic and the level of difficulty for the training materials and learning path topic were identified. Subsequent refinements were carried out by a smaller working group composed of the authors and maintainers of the Learning Path, as this stage required detailed discussion that would not have been effective in a larger group. This allowed the Data Management for Researchers Learning Path to be finalised on time. For the Data Stewardship Learning Path, a somewhat different approach was adopted: a core group worked on the LP asynchronously to progress its development.

The open and inclusive approach adopted throughout the process enabled contributions from all interested community members. However, several challenges were also identified. For example, workshop participants had varying levels of experience in RDM and training, which meant that some training materials initially assigned to specific topics were not appropriate. As a result, a detailed review and curation of all training resources identified by the Community was required by the authors and maintainers of the ELIXIR Data Management for Researchers Learning Path.

For the Data Stewardship Learning Path, identified challenges included gaps in available training materials for specific topics, limited visibility of governance, data stewardship roles, domain architecture and semantic interoperability in TeSS, difficulties in finding and structuring materials into coherent learning paths, inconsistent annotation and quality assessment of resources, limited coverage of policies beyond Data Management Plan focused workshops, and the challenge of integrating diverse national curricula and existing pathways into TeSS in a sustainable and maintainable way.

These experiences have provided valuable insights that can inform and streamline future community-based Learning Path development efforts within ELIXIR.

Outcomes and expected impact

The objectives of this task were successfully achieved through the publication of the [ELIXIR Data Management for Researchers Learning Path](#), marking a significant milestone as **the first ELIXIR Learning Path made available in TeSS**. The Learning Path provides a visible and structured entry point to RDM training resources curated across the ELIXIR network, improving discoverability and accessibility of high-quality training materials. In addition, it establishes a reusable and scalable framework that can be adopted by other ELIXIR Communities for the development of future Learning Paths.

As a result of this work, the ELIXIR Community now benefits from a tried-and-tested process for the development, curation, and maintenance of Learning Paths. This process is supported by defined maintainer roles and coordinated through the [ELIXIR Learning Paths group](#), strengthening community ownership and enabling long-term sustainability. The distributed, community-driven model adopted also increases the reuse of existing high-quality training resources, reduces duplication of effort across ELIXIR Nodes, and promotes alignment of training provision across the network.

For the Data Stewardship Learning Path, work is ongoing and will continue in the coming period, including a formal review by the ELIXIR Learning Path Focus Group, with publication in TeSS as the intended outcome.

Overall, this task delivered the following key outcomes:

- Publication of the [ELIXIR Data Management for Researchers Learning Path in TeSS](#), providing a structured overview of RDM training resources contributed by multiple ELIXIR Nodes.
- Advanced development of the ELIXIR Data Steward Learning Path, preparing for publication in TeSS.
- Development of a blueprint approach for future ELIXIR Community Learning Path initiatives.
- Establishment of a collaborative group of RDM, DS and training experts contributing to the design and curation of the Learning Path.
- Appointment of designated maintainers to support the ongoing curation, evolution, and sustainability of the Data Management for Researchers Learning Path.

Next steps and recommendations

The Data Management for Researchers Learning Path is the first official ELIXIR Learning Path published in TeSS. Additionally, as a next step, the Data Steward Learning Path will be finalised and published in TeSS. Its development provided an opportunity to test and refine the [ELIXIR Learning Paths Standard Operating Procedure](#) (SOP), which was established in July 2025 and operational since. It also provided an opportunity to test the newly Learning Paths implemented TeSS features and provide feedback on improvements and issues met during the development of the learning path in TeSS. A summary of the relevant TeSS issues submitted on GitHub are provided in Table 1.

GitHub Issue title	GitHub Issue Number
ELIXIR Learning Paths process inclusion when registering new learning paths	1200
Introduce ELIXIR Learning Path banner for ELIXIR Learning Paths to distinguish from other Learning Paths	1191
Learning Path - content as a collection (unordered)	1169
Introducing Maintainers for Learning Paths	1170
Learning Path - adding LP Collaborators as Topic Collaborators	1181
Learning Paths feature - no scroll bar in LP description area	1215

Table 1: GitHub issues created in the TeSS GitHub repository following discussions in the Data Management for Researchers Learning Path development team and ELIXIR Learning Paths Focus Group.

To ensure that ELIXIR Learning Paths are clearly distinguishable from other Learning Paths in TeSS and adequately support the ELIXIR multi-institutional approach, targeted improvements are required. This multi-institutional, community-driven model represents a key unique selling point (USP) of the ELIXIR Learning Paths framework.

A key recommendation is the introduction of a formal Maintainer role for ELIXIR Learning Paths. Maintainers would act as key contacts for each Learning Path and would be responsible for its ongoing curation and sustainability, supported by the ELIXIR Learning Paths Focus Group. This structure would allow Learning Paths to evolve over time by incorporating new content from across the ELIXIR community, while avoiding duplication, and enabling collaboration between different institutions, ensuring alignment with open and FAIR training practices.

A key element of the ELIXIR Learning Paths development process, as defined in the ELIXIR Learning Paths Standard Operating Procedure (SOP), is the inclusion of lead representatives from the ELIXIR Learning Paths Focus Group, the TeSS team, and the relevant ELIXIR Community. This step is critical for bringing together the different stakeholders involved in the development of a Learning Path and for fostering a collaborative, transparent, and inclusive approach that promotes shared understanding and agreement across all parties.

This multi-stakeholder model and the community development approach was successfully trialled during the development of the ELIXIR Data Management for Researchers Learning Path and proved essential in aligning technical, pedagogical, and community perspectives. It is therefore recommended that future ELIXIR Learning Paths adopt the same approach in line with the new ELIXIR Learning Paths SOP. Doing so will help avoid duplication of effort, support the adoption of open and collaborative practices, and facilitate effective coordination across the diverse teams and institutions that make up a large, distributed infrastructure such as ELIXIR.

Dissemination Plans

The [ELIXIR Data Management for Researchers Learning Path is published in TeSS](#) and is publicly accessible. Dissemination activities will include promotion through ELIXIR communication channels, such as the ELIXIR newsletter, to raise awareness among other ELIXIR Communities and encourage adoption of the ELIXIR Learning Paths framework and Standard Operating Procedure.

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